

TEXNIKA TA'LIM YO'NALISHLARIDA ELEKTR TEXNIK MATERIALLAR
FANINI O'QITISHDA ZAMONAVIY PEDAGOGIK TEXNOLOGILARNI
QO'LLASH SAMARADORLIGI

Xalilova Feruza Abdulvosiyevna¹

¹Farg'ona politexnika instituti

Khalilova Feruza Abdulvosiyevna²

²Fergana Polytechnic Institute

Mahammadjonov Qudratbek Ulug'bek o'g'li³

³Farg'ona politexnika instituti

Mahammadjonov Kudratbek Ulugbek ugli⁴

⁴Fergana politexnika institute

mahammadjonovqudratbek@gmail.com

f.xalilova@ferpi.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7219836>

Annotasiya: Ushbu maqolada "Elektr texnika materialari" fanini o'qitishning asosiy maqsadi, fanni o'qitishda interfaol metodlardan foydalangan xolda ma'ruza hamda amaliy mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etish, "Munosibini toping" metodidan foydalanish davomida talabalar mavzu bo'yicha bilimlarini mustaxkamlash va metod ahamiyati haqida ma'lumotlar yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: pedagog, pedagogik texnologiya, elektr texnik materiallar, metod, ma'ruza, "Munosibini toping".

Abstract: This article describes the organization of lectures and practical classes using interactive methods for the purpose of teaching the discipline "Electrical Materials", tells about the importance and application of the "Find a match" method to consolidate the knowledge gained on the topic.

Key words: pedagogue, pedagogical technology, electrotechnical materials, method, lecture, "Find a match".

Bugungi kunda respublika oliy ta'lim muassasasilari yangi "O'quv jarayonini modernizatsiyalash va oliy ta'lim tizimi o'quv-metodik faoliyatiga innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni tadbiq qilish dasturi"ni bajarilishi ustida ish olib borishmoqda. Ma'lumki, oliy ta'lim islohotlari – eng avvalo raqobatbardosh mutaxassislarni tayyorlash va mehnat bozoriga yo'naltirilgandir. Zamonaviy innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining bir tizimga solingan ilmiy-nazariy hamda metodik asoslangan yangi shakl, usul va vositalarining majmuidir. Bunda yangi mazmun, shakl, usul va vosita uyg'unligida maqsad, vazifa, faoliyat va pedagogik natija yaxlitligi ta'minlanadi hamda o'quv maqsadlariga erishishni kafolatlaydigan o'quv jarayoni loyihalashtiriladi va amalga oshiriladi.

Texnika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida talabalarning "Elektr texnika materiallari" fanini o'zlashtirishlari uchun o'qitishning ilg'or va zamonaviy usullaridan foydalanish, yangi informatsion-pedagogik texnologiyalarini tadbiq etish muhim ahamiyatga egadir. Fanni o'zlashtirishda darslik, o'quv va uslubiy qo'llanma hamda ko'rsatmalar, ma'ruza matnlari, tarqatma materiallar, elektron materiallar, virtual stendlar, ishchi holatdagi elektr texnik materiallarining namunalari va maketlaridan foydalaniladi. Ma'ruza va amaliy darslarda mos ravishdagi ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalaniladi.

Pedagogik texnologiya – bu ta'lim shakllarini optimallashtirish masalani qo'yuvchi, texnik va insoniy imkoniyatlarni va ularning o'zaro munosabatlarini hisobga olib o'qitish va bilimlar o'zlashtirish butun jarayonini yaratish, qo'llash va belgilashga sistemali yondashishidir.

Har qanday innovatsiyada "yangi", "yangilik" tushunchalari muhim ahamiyatga ega. Turli munosabat va jarayonlarga kiritiladigan yangilik mazmunan xususiy, sub'ektiv, mahalliy va shartli g'oyalar tarzida namoyon bo'ladi. Xususiy yangilik munosabat, ob'ekt yoki jarayonga tegishli elementlardan birini o'zgartirish, yangilashni nazarida tutadi [1.120].

Texnika oliy ta'lim muassasalarida yetuk kadrlar tayyorlashda texnik, ya'ni mutaxassislik fanlaridan biri "Elektrotexnika materiallari" fanini o'qitishdan asosiy maqsad, elektr jihozlarini muntazam ravishda o'rganish, qulay va samarali bo'lishini ta'minlash hamda tashkiliy tadbirlarni tuza bilish va ularni amalga oshirishdan iboratdir. "Elektrotexnika materiallari" fanini o'qitish jarayonida talabalarga elektr jihozlarini (tuzilishi, turlari, ishlashi) sifatida elektr jihozlarini ish faoliyat ko'rsatishlari uchun zarur nazariy bilimlar hamda amaliy ko'nikmalar o'rgatiladi [3,4].

Talabalar fanni mukammal o'rganish uchun, elektr texnika materiallarining klassifikatsiyalari xaqidagi tushunchalarni chuqur o'zlashtirishlari, unda o'rgangan bilimlarini elektr texnikasida qo'llay bilishlari zarur. Shuning uchun ularga bilim berish jarayonida yangi ilg'or pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanib dars mashg'ulotlarini olib borib zarur. Chunki, ushbu fan xozirda dastlabki bosqich talabalariga olib borilishi sababli, ularni fanga qiziqтира ola bilish, o'zlashtirishlari uchun qulay bo'lish yo'llarini qo'llagan holda dars mashg'ulotlarini olib bori kerak.

Ma'ruza mashg'ulotlarini zamonaviy usullarda samarali tashkil etish talabalarning axborotlarni o'zlashtirish, sintezlashi va ularni to'la egallash faolligini ta'minlaydi. Ma'ruza mashg'ulotlarini o'rganish jarayonida talabalarning fikrlash faoliyatining turli tuman ko'rinishlari namoyon bo'ladi.

Bunda jarayon yanada ongli ravishda o'zlashtiriladi. O'rganish va tanqidiy fikrlash talabalarning aniq vazifalarga nisbatan yangi bilimlarni qo'llash imkoniyatlariga ega bo'lgan taqdirda rivojlanadi. O'rganish talabalarning oldingi bilimlarini yanada mustahkamlanadi. Talabalarning olgan bilimlarini yangi axborotlar bilan bog'lash imkoniyati yaratiladi.

Yaratilgan imkoniyatlardan kelib chiqib, "Elektr texnik materiallar" fanini o'qitishda "Dielektr materiallarida energiya isrofi" mavzusida olib borilgan ma'ruza mashg'uloti yakunida oddiy, sodda, ko'p vaqt talab qilmaydigan interfaol metodlarni qo'llash maqsadga muvofiq bo'ladi. Shunday metodlardan biri "Munosibini toping" metodi bo'lib, talabalarni olgan bilimlarini mustahkamlashlarini ta'minlaydi.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytishimiz mumkinki, innovatsion faoliyat pedagogning ruhiy, aqliy, jismoniy kuchini ma'lum maqsadga yo'naltirish asosida nazariy bilim, amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni egallash, amaliy faoliyatni nazariy bilimlar bilan to'ldirib borish, bilish, loyihalash, kommunikativ nutq va tashkilotchilik mahoratini rivojlantirishni talab etadi. Bu borada taklif qilinayotgan "Munosibini toping" metodidan foydalanish davomida talabalar mavzu bo'yicha bilimlarini mustaxkamlash uchun berilgan tushunchalarni o'qib, to'g'risini tanlash uchun fikr bildiradi. Bu esa talabalarni umumiy qamrab olish imkoniyatini yaratadi. Talabadan nimanidur bilishini og'zaki so'rash bilan belgilangan vaqtda kam sonli talabalar qamrab olinadi. Taklif qilinayotgan metod orqali esa talabalarni umumiy qamrab olish bilan ularning bilimlarini mustaxkamlash mumkin bo'ladi. Bu metodni amalga oshirish uchun kompyuter texnologiyalaridan foydalanish zarur bo'lganligi uchun kompyuter texnologiyalarining boshqa imkoniyatlaridan ham foydalanish joizdir, metod maxsus programma orqali bajarilsa natijasi ham avtomatik ravishda chiqarib beriladi. Natijaga ko'ra talabalar belgilangan mavzu bo'yicha tuzilgan munosib javoblarni berganliklariga qarab, o'z bilimlariga o'zlari baho berishadi. Bunday metodlarda talaba va o'qituvchi birga faol ishtirok etayotganligi uchun interfaol metod sanalib, talabalarda yanada qiziqish uyg'otadi. Fanlardan mavzular boyicha olingan bilim-ko'nikmalarni mustaxkamlashda biz taklif qilayotgan "Munosibini toping" metodi yaxshi samara berishi shubxasizdir.

Today, the republic's higher educational institutions have a new "Education They are working on the implementation of the program of modernizing the process and applying innovative pedagogical technologies to the educational and methodological activities of the higher education system. It is known that higher education reforms are primarily aimed at training competitive specialists

and the labor market. Modern innovative pedagogical technologies are a set of new forms, methods and tools of the educational process, integrated into one system, based on scientific-theoretical and methodological basis. In this case, the integrity of the goal, task, activity, and pedagogical result is ensured in the combination of new content, form, method, and tool, and the educational process that guarantees the achievement of educational goals is designed and implemented.

In technical higher education institutions, it is important to use advanced and modern methods of teaching, to apply new informational and pedagogical technologies in order for students to master the science of "Electrical engineering materials". Textbooks, educational and methodological manuals and instructions, lecture texts, handouts, electronic materials, virtual stands, samples and models of electrical technical materials in working condition are used in mastering the subject. Appropriate advanced pedagogical technologies are used in lectures and practical lessons.

Pedagogical technology is a systematic approach to the creation, application and determination of the entire process of teaching and learning, taking into account the technical and human capabilities and their mutual relations.

The concepts of "new" and "innovation" are important in any innovation. Innovation introduced into various attitudes and processes is manifested in the form of private, subjective, local and conditional ideas. Private innovation means changing, updating one of the elements related to a relationship, object or process [1.120]. The main goal of teaching "Electrotechnic materials" as one of the technical, i.e., specialty subjects in the training of advanced personnel in technical higher education institutions is to regularly study electrical equipment, to ensure that it is convenient and effective, and to be able to organize organizational events. and their implementation. In the course of teaching the subject of "Electrical engineering materials", students are taught the necessary theoretical knowledge and practical skills for the operation of electrical equipment as electrical equipment (structure, types, operation) [3,4].

In order to learn the science perfectly, students need to thoroughly master the concepts of the classification of electrical engineering materials, and be able to apply the knowledge they have learned in electrical engineering. Therefore, in the process of imparting knowledge to them, it is necessary to conduct lessons using new advanced pedagogical technologies. Because this subject is currently taught to students of the first stage, it is necessary to conduct classes using ways

to make them interested in the subject and to make it convenient for them to master it.

Effective organization of lectures in modern ways ensures students' active assimilation and synthesis of information and their full mastery. In the process of studying lecture classes, different aspects of students' thinking activity are revealed. In this case, the process is mastered more consciously. Learning and critical thinking develop when students have opportunities to apply new knowledge to specific tasks. Learning will strengthen students' previous knowledge. An opportunity is created to connect the acquired knowledge of students with new information.

Based on the created opportunities, it is appropriate to use simple, simple, interactive methods that do not require a lot of time at the end of the lecture session on the topic "Energy waste in dielectric materials" in the teaching of "Electrical technical materials". . One such method is the "Find the Match" method, which ensures students to consolidate the knowledge they have acquired.

In conclusion, we can say that the innovative activity of the pedagogue theoretical knowledge based on directing one's spiritual, mental, and physical strength to a certain goal, acquisition of practical skills and qualifications, practical activity with theoretical knowledge filling, knowledge, design, communicative speech and organizational skills requires development. In this regard, during the use of the proposed "Find the Correspondence" method, students read the given concepts to strengthen their knowledge on the subject and express their opinion in order to choose the right one. This creates an opportunity for general inclusion of students. Asking the student verbally what they know will cover a small number of students in the allotted time. Through the proposed method, it will be possible to strengthen students' knowledge with general coverage. Since it is necessary to use computer technologies to implement this method, it is permissible to use other possibilities of computer technologies. According to the results, students evaluate their own knowledge depending on whether they have given appropriate answers on the given topic. Since the student and the teacher actively participate in such methods, it is considered an interactive method, which arouses more interest in students. There is no doubt that the "Find the relationship" method offered by us will be effective in strengthening the knowledge and skills acquired in subjects.

Adabiyotlar:

1. Ishmuhamedov R.J., M.Mirsolieva. O'quv jarayonida innovatsion ta'lim texnologiyalari. – T.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2014. 60 b.

2. Yo'ldoshev J.G', Usmonov S.A. Pedagogik texnologiya asoslari: qo'llanma. – T.: “O'qituvchi”, 2004. - 104 b.
3. Xalilova F.A. Improvement of Teaching Methods in Electrical Materials in Universities.- Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology, 2021, Pages. 14564-14570.
4. Xalilova F.A., Nasretdinova F.N. The factors accelerating the innovative activity of teachers //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – T. 11. – №. 4. – C. 1090-1094
5. F. N.Nasretdinova, A.V. Ashurov, F.A.Xalilova. Efficiency of using information resources and technology in students research work //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2020. – T. 10. – C. 1680-1684.

